

IN THE WORKS OF EASTERN THINKERS - ILLUMINATION OF A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE

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Abstract. *This article discusses the opinions of some eastern thinkers about a healthy lifestyle, human health, the constant movement of the body, and how important work is for a person.*

Keywords: *medicine, labor, movement, food culture, spirituality, education of a healthy generation.*

The idea of creating a healthy generation has been born since the beginning of mankind, and it is developing step by step. In the East, maintaining the balance of a person's physical and spiritual condition was considered an important principle.

In 82-83 years of the 11th century, Kaikovus ibn Iskandar, the grandson of the king of Western Iran, dedicated the work "Nightmare" to his son Gilonshah. Kaikovus, the author of "Nightmare" work, was one of the thinkers of his time, and he had multifaceted knowledge like the Eastern encyclopedic scholars. Judging by the information, he "perfectly mastered medicine, catastrophism, and spiritual knowledge" [1]. Therefore, in this work, along with moral education, medical rules related to human health are given a wide place. In particular, it describes the science of medicine, the ethics of doctors, physical education, nutrition, sleep, healthy upbringing of a child, dress code, various vices, i.e. the harmful consequences of drinking wine, engaging in fornication, and other issues. The thirty-third chapter of "Nightmare" is about medicine, and it encourages a person to follow the etiquette of a healthy life. Kaikovus emphasizes that a person should always work, his body should be in motion. Work, he says, saves the body from laziness and idleness, idleness leads to corruption and sickness of the body. When the body is empty, in motionless pleasure, it commands you. He is forced to act, not willingly, he has no incentive to do anything until you tell him to. As Kaikovus said: "If everyone controls his own body, he can also control the body of others, because if everyone controls his own body, by learning virtue and skill, he will create health and honor of two worlds." The capital of all wisdom and craft is: decency, modesty, honesty, moderation, gentleness, patience and perseverance" [2]. One of the main reasons for human health is the observance of food culture. Restrain lust, eat food on time, do not overeat in the evening, eat in moderation, have a free, open face while eating, treat food with respect, do not discriminate between good and bad food, when a lot of food is brought, first of all show compliments to others, not to oneself, in front of others Obedience to dietary rules, such as sharing food with them, is a guarantee of health. He also says: "O child, if there is food, call your companions so that they can eat your food, but eat the food quickly and bend gently." Do not talk to people while eating, this is a requirement of Islam, but keep your head down and do not look at the open mouth of your companions" [2]. In his chapter "On Sleep and Rest" Kaikovus says: "Sleeping too much is harmful, so too much sleep is harmful. For example, if a person is carried without sleep for seventy-two hours, that is, three days and four nights, there is a danger of sudden death. However, there is a measure to everything. For example, sages say that there are twenty-four hours in day and night (two-thirds awake, one-third sleep). Devote eight hours to

livelihood work, eight hours to joy and spiritual joy, and eight hours to give rest to the members who are tired of sixteen hours of work. These recommendations in "Nightmare" have not lost their importance even in our time.

Abu Ali ibn Sina, who was one of the founders of the healthy lifestyle, defined medicine as "Medicine is a science in which the condition of the human body is studied in terms of health and disease, its existing health is preserved and lost health is restored" [3]. This definition given by Ibn Sina has not lost its importance even today. In his works, the great physician emphasized the importance of a healthy lifestyle in health care, and in his recommendations aimed at health care and strengthening, he recommended proper nutrition, regular physical education, mental health, keeping the body clean, sexual education, and hygiene rules to prevent diseases. He emphasized that it is important. Ibn Sina, as a scientist in the field of medicine, attached great importance to the correct diagnosis of patients and their successful treatment, and understood that the task of practical medicine is to maintain people's health and prevent diseases. He prioritized this task in his medical career, developed a number of activities aimed at maintaining health and preventing diseases and showed the ways of their implementation. In the words of Ibn Sina, the main condition for maintaining health is to ensure the moderation of general factors that are important for human life. This requires specific knowledge, education and upbringing. The main health measures developed and recommended by Ibn Sina are as follows:

1. Pay special attention to the balance of physical and mental activities.
2. Choosing the right things to eat and drink.
3. To ensure the balance of rest, sleep and wakefulness.
4. Paying attention to sufficient and moderate breathing air.
5. Wear clothes according to the body and the season.
6. Regularly cleaning the body (organism) from various wastes.
7. To ensure that one's temperament is in a moderate state.
8. Maintaining the norm of body (organism) weight.

Abu Ali ibn Sina put physical education, i.e., physical activities, in the first place among health measures. He considered physical education to be the most important and fundamental factor in health care. He put eating habits in the second place, rest and sleep in the third place. Abu Ali ibn Sina, in his teachings and recommendations on medicine, showed that every person should determine a healthy lifestyle for himself based on the structure of his body, internal and external capabilities, level of health and mentality, and follow it regularly. The great doctor said that it is easier to prevent various diseases than to cure them.

Abu Rayhan Beruni, one of the scholars, also interprets the idea of raising a healthy generation in his own way. Even though Beruni did not create a perfect systemized doctrine of society and social events like Beruni Farobi, as a great scientist, he expressed his views on issues such as society, human social life, and human happiness, which are extremely important issues for all times. The great encyclopedist Abu Rayhan Beruni said: "Liberty and mediocrity should be the core of nobility, and talking about the fact that a person's external appearance is directly related to his moral image, he said that it is necessary to "brush the teeth, keep the eyes and eyelids clean, put antimony on them, and take care of the nails" » expresses the opinion that in addition to health, such qualities ensure the beauty and purity of a person. He believes that when a person controls his passions, educates his soul and body, he is able to turn his negative aspects into positive things, treat them with spiritual medicine and gradually eliminate them" [4].

In conclusion, we can say that the comfort, peace, care, respect, dignity, sincere kindness necessary for a person - in short, noble human feelings and qualities begin with a healthy environment and a healthy lifestyle. Its roots sprout, grow and bear fruit in the process of a healthy family, education and upbringing. And these develop based on the spiritual, spiritual and moral aspects of a healthy lifestyle and acquire a new essence and improve. It is desirable to organize a healthy lifestyle in current conditions based on ethical criteria specific to the demands of our time.

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